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Assessing The Usage Of Modern Technologies In The Teaching Of Business Education Courses In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the usage of modern technologies in the teaching of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The areas of modern technologies considered were its Availability, Adequacy, Utilization, Challenges Encountered by Business Education Lecturers in the Utilization of Modern Technologies for Teaching Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions and Remedies to the Challenges Encountered by Business Education Lecturers in the Utilization of Modern Technologies for Teaching Business Education Courses in Tertiary Institutions. Likewise, the moderating influence of gender, type of institution, and educational qualification were also examined. Five research questions were raised and answered, while five null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 140 business education lecturers. The entire population of 140 business education lecturers were used hence, the census sampling technique was adopted because of the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection was a 75-item structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) value obtained for the instruments showed a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data collected from the respondents were analysed using Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test Statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings of the study revealed that Modern technologies are moderately available for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State and that these Modern technologies are rarely utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that modern technologies are rarely utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. It was recommended among others that Stakeholders of tertiary institutions should provide sufficient resources to keep up with the evolving technological landscape in business education.

Keywords: business education, modern technologies, teaching

INTRODUCTION

Following political independence, numerous African nations, including Nigeria, embarked on extensive reforms targeting key sectors of society. A major focus of these efforts was the transformation of educational systems to better reflect each country's unique developmental goals and societal needs. In Nigeria's case, significant adjustments were made to its educational framework to support national

aspirations, acknowledging education as a fundamental driver of socio-economic progress (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). To achieve long-term objectives such as Vision 20:2020 and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Nigerian government mandated the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council to overhaul the national curriculum. This reform was intended to keep pace with the dynamic needs of society. In response, the Federal Government introduced the Business Education programme, designed to equip students with practical vocational skills and competencies through the use of specialized tools and equipment.

Business Education in Nigeria is diverse, covering a range of subject areas. Its primary goal is to empower students with job-ready skills, thereby enhancing their employability. Ubulom (2014) emphasizes that the programme aims to provide a pathway to meaningful employment. Similarly, Otamiri (2014) defines business education as a discipline that integrates technological knowledge, scientific principles, and hands-on training to prepare individuals for various occupational roles within both the public and private sectors. The effectiveness of any educational system depends greatly on how well it delivers relevant knowledge and practical skills applicable in real-life contexts.

Accordingly, the objectives of Business Education in Nigeria include preparing competent professionals in fields such as management, secretarial work, marketing, accounting, and banking; training qualified teachers and lecturers for business-related disciplines; fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and business culture; and equipping graduates with the skills necessary to launch and manage their own enterprises.

Despite these well-intentioned efforts, there is growing concern over the competency of Business Education graduates, particularly in the area of technological proficiency. As observed by Nwokocha (2015), the adoption of modern instructional technologies in Nigerian classrooms remains limited. Traditional teaching methods still dominate, offering minimal interactive learning opportunities and slow feedback. In contrast, digital learning tools provide enhanced engagement, faster assessment processes, and flexible learning environments—features that far surpass the capabilities of conventional teaching methods.

The growing trend of globalization in education has significantly accelerated the adoption of digital technologies. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, online platforms were already in use for conducting lectures, distributing academic materials, evaluating students, and managing institutional operations. Nevertheless, their application was more optional than essential. The outbreak of COVID-19 in 2020 compelled educational institutions across the globe to shift fully to digital modes of instruction to maintain academic continuity. While developed nations were relatively prepared for this transition, many developing countries had to adapt swiftly and often with difficulty. In this context, digital technology became the cornerstone of education delivery during the crisis. The pandemic emphasized the importance of aligning national education systems with global digital standards. These technologies not only support learning but also foster critical professional skills, including analytical thinking, problem-solving, structured reasoning, and understanding complex processes. Furthermore, they equip students for a future characterized by constant change and technological advancement.

Nigeria's *National Policy on Education* (FRN, 2014) stresses the importance of integrating digital tools into education. It acknowledges the critical role of information and communication technology (ICT) in enhancing the knowledge and skills essential for functioning effectively in the modern world. Consequently, the policy advocates for urgent incorporation of ICT into all levels of education in Nigeria. Many academic institutions are now focusing on enhancing their programmes by incorporating digital technologies, aiming to create more flexible teaching and learning environments. As noted by Inije et al. (2013), numerous institutions worldwide have begun to use digital tools not only to complement traditional in-person teaching but also as viable alternatives for delivering educational content. Similarly, Nigerian institutions are increasingly recognizing these technologies as valuable solutions for improving instructional delivery.

Digital tools are gaining prominence in higher education, where they serve diverse functions such as tutoring, course administration, interactive learning, simulations, programming, and problem-solving exercises. Their major advantage lies in enabling experiential learning via web-based applications. The internet offers countless free and practical resources suitable for educational purposes. These digital

technologies are applicable across all facets of business education. The extent to which they are utilized depends largely on the creativity and initiative of educators. The rapid advancement in digital tools can also be attributed to growing demand and widespread availability. Teachers and students increasingly favor them for their affordability, ease of access, ability to overcome geographical barriers, and suitability for customized, on-demand learning. They also support diverse teaching strategies, including simulations, interactive modules, and self-paced formats.

As highlighted by Iyamu and Chiedu (2020), the use of digital technologies is now integral to the effective management of modern organizations. Their application in educational administration has offered innovative solutions to challenges that might have otherwise remained unresolved through traditional methods. According to Mashau and Andrisha (2016), educators and learners must embrace innovation within the educational system to enhance the teaching and learning processes, particularly in business education, by effectively incorporating modern technologies.

Modern technology stands as a critical driver of global economic transformation and rapid societal change. It has significantly altered how individuals learn, interact, and conduct business. In the realm of education, technological advancements have reshaped both the location and nature of learning, as well as redefined the roles of educators and learners. Essentially, modern technology represents refined scientific innovations designed to simplify tasks and enhance efficiency. Within this context, technologies such as computers, word processors, internet services, automated teller machines (ATMs), reprographic and micrographic equipment, accounting tools, advanced telecommunication systems (including smartphones), and multimedia devices have not only revolutionized office operations but have also transformed daily routines and practices.

Ojo and Bashir (2020) identified several emerging digital tools, including PowerPoint presentations, blogs, mobile applications, iTunes, screen recording, augmented and virtual reality, Twitter, wikis, voice threads, speech recognition systems, web conferencing, video conferencing, YouTube, interactive whiteboards, online libraries, databases, LCD projectors, internet-enabled phones, and multifunctional hybrid devices. These technologies often support widely accepted file formats such as HTML, PDF, GIF, JPEG, and MPEG, which enhance compatibility and ease of use across platforms.

Despite the broad benefits these tools offer to the business environment, there appears to be a gap in the ability of business education graduates to effectively operate such technologies. This may be due to limited exposure during their training or the absence of technology-integrated instruction in their academic programmes. Consequently, many business education graduates struggle with employability, especially when compared to their peers in fields like Business Administration and Accounting, who are often perceived as more technologically adept. Additionally, some students maintain a preference for traditional teaching methods—such as note-taking and lecture-based instruction—which may hinder their preparedness for the demands of modern workplaces. This reliance on outdated learning methods only becomes problematic after graduation when they encounter real-world job requirements.

Given these concerns, it becomes important to assess the availability, sufficiency, and practical application of modern technologies in the instruction of Business Education courses. It is also essential to identify the challenges hindering their effective use and explore viable solutions. Therefore, the primary goal of this study is to investigate the extent to which digital technologies are utilized in teaching Business Education in tertiary institutions across Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

Evidence suggests that many tertiary institutions in Delta State have yet to fully incorporate digital technologies into their Business Education programmes. During on-site visits by the research team, several challenges were identified that hinder effective integration. These include limited financial resources, inconsistent electricity supply, recurrent power outages, poor technological infrastructure, low internet bandwidth, lack of internet access, insufficient and outdated software, inadequate integration of ICT into teaching practices, and a shortage of qualified personnel skilled in using digital tools.

In addition, many institutions either lack sufficient computers or do not have well-equipped computer laboratories. Even where such facilities exist, the absence of trained technical staff to manage and maintain the equipment points to a broader issue—namely, the insufficient commitment of key

stakeholders to fully digitalize Business Education in these institutions. If these challenges persist, students may graduate with limited exposure to ICT-driven instruction, ultimately affecting their technological competence and job readiness. It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to evaluate the extent to which modern technologies are being utilized in the teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions across Delta State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent are modern technological tools available for the instruction of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions within Delta State?
2. How sufficient are the available modern technologies for effectively teaching Business Education courses in these institutions?
3. To what degree are modern technologies being applied in the teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions across Delta State?
4. What challenges do Business Education lecturers face when employing modern technologies for instructional purposes in tertiary institutions?
5. What strategies can be implemented to overcome the difficulties encountered by Business Education lecturers in using modern technologies for teaching in tertiary institutions?

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this research is to evaluate the application of modern technological tools in teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions across Delta State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Examine the level of availability of modern technologies for instructing Business Education courses.
2. Determine the adequacy of such technologies in facilitating effective teaching and learning;
3. Assess how frequently and effectively these modern technologies are used by lecturers in Business Education;
4. Identify the obstacles Business Education lecturers encounter in utilizing technological tools during instruction; and
5. Recommend solutions to address the challenges faced by lecturers when integrating modern technologies into their teaching practices.

Research Hypotheses

To guide this study, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 significance level:

1. There is no statistically significant difference between male and female lecturers regarding the availability of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. There is no statistically significant difference in the perceptions of university and college of education lecturers on the adequacy of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses.
3. There is no significant variation in responses based on lecturers' academic qualifications concerning the extent of utilization of modern technologies in teaching Business Education courses.
4. There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers regarding the challenges they face in using modern technologies for instructional purposes.
5. There is no statistically significant difference based on educational qualification in the responses of lecturers on the proposed solutions to the challenges of using modern technologies in Business Education classrooms.

Significance of the Study

The findings from this study will be highly valuable to key stakeholders including institutional administrators, lecturers, students, and future researchers in related disciplines.

For institutional management, the study will offer a clearer perspective on the current state of digital infrastructure in Business Education. This insight will support more informed planning and policy

decisions. With accurate data on technological gaps and strengths, school authorities can better prioritize and allocate resources to improve ICT facilities and training. This will foster a more effective teaching and learning environment through enhanced technology integration.

Moreover, the results of the study will support the development of forward-looking strategies aligned with institutional goals. Administrators will be better equipped to establish policies, form beneficial partnerships, and invest in long-term improvements to digital infrastructure. In addition, the study may highlight areas where lecturers require further training, enabling the design of targeted professional development programmes that improve educators' competence in using educational technology.

Lecturers stand to benefit from the study as well. It will provide them with a clearer understanding of the digital tools available within their institutions, helping them incorporate suitable technologies into their teaching. The study's findings may also promote professional growth by identifying knowledge gaps and training needs, encouraging continuous skill enhancement in educational technologies. This not only enriches lecturers' teaching approaches but also ensures they remain current with technological trends in education.

Students will equally gain from the outcomes of this research. By highlighting strengths and weaknesses in the current digital learning environment, the study may lead to better access to modern instructional tools. This improved access will enhance student engagement and understanding, equipping them with the relevant technological competencies needed in today's job market. Addressing issues like limited internet access or outdated devices will help create a more supportive and interactive learning environment.

The academic community and future researchers will also benefit. This study will contribute fresh data and contextual insights into the integration of technology in Business Education. Researchers can use the findings as a foundation for future investigations, comparative studies, or extended inquiries into digital pedagogy. Additionally, the study can serve as a benchmark for examining how technological developments influence teaching effectiveness and learning outcomes in higher education. Ultimately, it will add to the growing body of knowledge on technology-driven education and inspire further innovations in teaching and learning practices.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This research is centered on evaluating the extent to which modern technologies are applied in the teaching and learning of Business Education courses. Specifically, it addresses issues related to the availability, sufficiency, and usage of technological tools, the challenges faced by lecturers, and proposed solutions to enhance the integration of technology in instructional practices.

The study is delimited to public tertiary institutions in Delta State that offer Business Education programmes. It does not cover private institutions or disciplines outside the scope of Business Education.

RESEARCH METHOD AND PROCEDURE

This section outlines the research methodology adopted for the study. The discussions are structured under the following subheadings: area of the study, research design, population, sample and sampling techniques, research instrument, validity and reliability of the instrument, methods of data collection, and data analysis procedures.

Area of the Study

The research was carried out in Delta State, located in the southern region of Nigeria. It shares boundaries with Edo State to the north, Anambra and Rivers States to the east, Bayelsa State to the south, and the Bight of Benin to the west. Delta State's capital is Asaba, while Warri serves as the state's main economic hub. Established on August 27, 1991, the state is recognized for its vast natural resources, multi-ethnic population, and significant role in Nigeria's educational and economic sectors.

Research Design

A descriptive survey design was employed in this study. This design is used to gather data that describes events or conditions as they exist at a specific point in time. It involves collecting, organizing, and analyzing data from a representative sample of the population to gain insights into current practices or opinions (Akpojotor, 2022). This design was deemed appropriate for investigating the extent of modern

technological integration in the teaching and learning of Business Education in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Population of the Study

The target population included all Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions across Delta State. A total of 140 lecturers from five institutions formed the population of the study, as detailed in Table 3.1 below:

Table 3.1: Business Education Lecturers in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

S/N	Institution	Number of Lecturers
1	Delta State University, Abraka	22
2	University of Delta, Agbor	21
3	College of Education, Mosogar	10
4	College of Education, Warri	10
5	Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba	77
Total		140

Source: Heads of Business Education Departments, respective institutions (2025)

Sample and Sampling Technique: Given the manageable size of the population, the study employed a census sampling technique, which involved including all 140 Business Education lecturers from the identified institutions. This ensured that the findings would reflect the views of the entire population.

Research Instrument: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, divided into two sections. Section A focused on the demographic information of respondents, while Section B covered the core constructs of the study. Section B included five major areas:

- Availability of Modern Technologies
- Adequacy of Modern Technologies
- Utilization of Modern Technologies
- Challenges in Technology Utilization
- Solutions to Identified Challenges

Responses were rated using a four-point Likert scale, with different labels for each construct:

- Availability/Adequacy: Highly Available/Adequate (4), Moderately Available/Adequate (3), Scarcely Available/Adequate (2), Not Available/Adequate (1)
- Utilization: Highly Utilized (4), Moderately Utilized (3), Rarely Utilized (2), Not Utilized (1)
- Challenges and Remedies: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), Strongly Disagree (1)

The decision benchmark was defined as follows:

Response Option	Score	Boundary
Strongly Agree (SA)	4	3.50 – 4.00
Agree (A)	3	2.50 – 3.49
Disagree (D)	2	1.50 – 2.49
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	0.50 – 1.49

Validity of the Instrument

To ensure content and face validity, the instrument was reviewed by the researcher’s supervisor, a faculty member from the Department of Business Education, and a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation from Delta State University, Abraka. These experts assessed the relevance, structure, and clarity of the questionnaire. Feedback provided by the validators was incorporated before finalizing the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The test-retest reliability method was used to determine the consistency of the instrument. A pilot test was conducted involving 30 Business Education lecturers from Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, who were not part of the study population. The same instrument was administered twice within a two-week interval. Data from both tests were analyzed using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, which yielded a reliability score of 0.89, indicating a high level of reliability.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher, assisted by five trained personnel, personally distributed the questionnaires to the lecturers at their respective offices. Prior to distribution, necessary approvals were obtained from the Heads of Departments, and informed consent was secured from the respondents. All 140 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, resulting in a 100% return rate. Completed forms were checked for completeness before proceeding to data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were utilized. The mean and standard deviation were employed to address the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using independent samples t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 0.05 level of significance. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 24. A benchmark mean of 2.50 served as the cutoff point:

- Mean scores ≥ 2.50 indicated agreement
- Mean scores < 2.50 indicated disagreement

For hypothesis testing, the decision rule was as follows: if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted; if it is less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study are tabulated as follows:

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of availability of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on extent of availability of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
1.	Learning Management System	2.59	0.81	Moderately Available
2.	Google Classroom	2.57	0.78	Moderately Available
3.	Tablets	2.21	0.69	Scantly Available
4.	Smart phones	2.94	0.83	Moderately Available
5.	Laptops	2.51	0.69	Moderately Available
6.	Internet facilities	2.24	0.74	Scantly Available
7.	Projector	2.08	0.71	Scantly Available
8.	Scanner	2.04	0.65	Scantly Available
9.	Artificial Intelligence (AI)	3.04	0.75	Moderately Available
10.	Interactive Whiteboard	2.09	0.62	Scantly Available
11.	Virtual Reality (VR)	2.73	0.79	Moderately Available
12.	Canvas	2.63	0.82	Moderately Available
13.	Zoom	2.76	0.87	Moderately Available
14.	Google Meet	2.82	0.94	Moderately Available
15.	Google Docs	2.61	0.96	Moderately Available
	Grand Mean/SD	2.52	0.78	Moderately Available

The mean responses of the respondents on ten of the items in Table 4.1 ranged from 2.51 to 3.04 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 on a four point rating scale. While five of the items mean ranged from 2.04 to 2.24 which indicated that these items did not meet the cut-off point value of 2.50. However, the grand mean of 2.52 clearly indicated that the modern technologies are moderately available for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The standard deviation of the fifteen items in the scale ranged from 0.62 to 0.96 which displayed that the responses of the respondents were not far apart from the mean and to one another

Research Question 2: *How adequate are modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on extent of adequacy of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
1.	Learning Management System	2.76	0.90	Moderately Adequate
2.	Google Classroom	2.69	0.68	Moderately Adequate
3.	Tablets	2.33	0.73	Scantly Adequate
4.	Smart phones	3.02	0.84	Moderately Adequate
5.	Laptops	2.64	0.76	Moderately Adequate
6.	Internet facilities	2.39	0.89	Scantly Adequate
7.	Projector	2.28	0.87	Scantly Adequate
8.	Scanner	2.29	0.88	Scantly Adequate
9.	Artificial Intelligence (AI)	3.21	0.78	Moderately Adequate
10.	Interactive Whiteboard	2.49	0.99	Scantly Adequate
11.	Virtual Reality (VR)	3.01	0.85	Moderately Adequate
12.	Canvas	2.67	0.84	Moderately Adequate
13.	Zoom	2.80	0.70	Moderately Adequate
14.	Google Meet	2.49	0.82	Scantly Adequate
15.	Google Docs	2.47	0.88	Scantly Adequate
	Grand Mean/SD	2.64	0.83	Moderately Adequate

The mean responses of the respondents on eight of the items in Table 4.2 ranged from 2.64 to 3.21 which are greater than the bench mark of 2.50. While seven of the items mean ranged from 2.28 to 2.49 which indicated that these items did not meet the criterion mean of 2.50. However, the grand mean of 2.64 obviously showed that the modern technologies are moderately adequate for teaching business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The standard deviation of the fifteen items in the scale ranged from 0.68 to 0.99 which indicated that the responses of the respondents were close to the mean and to one another

Research Question 3: *What is the extent of utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.3: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on extent of utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
1.	Learning Management System	2.15	0.76	Rarely Utilized
2.	Google Classroom	2.23	0.70	Rarely Utilized
3.	Tablets	1.99	0.80	Rarely Utilized
4.	Smart phones	3.25	0.80	Moderately Utilized
5.	Laptops	3.42	0.80	Moderately Utilized
6.	Internet facilities	2.76	0.83	Moderately Utilized
7.	Projector	2.20	0.93	Rarely Utilized
8.	Scanner	2.71	0.84	Moderately Utilized
9.	Artificial Intelligence (AI)	3.36	0.85	Moderately Utilized
10.	Interactive Whiteboard	2.19	0.86	Rarely Utilized
11.	Virtual Reality (VR)	2.60	0.97	Moderately Utilized
12.	Canvas	2.12	0.90	Rarely Utilized
13.	Zoom	2.17	0.77	Rarely Utilized
14.	Google Meet	1.99	0.81	Rarely Utilized
15.	Google Docs	1.81	0.82	Rarely Utilized
	Grand Mean/SD	2.46	0.83	Rarely Utilized

From Table 4.3 it was clear that the mean responses of the respondents on six of the items ranged from 2.60 to 3.42 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. While nine of the items mean ranged from 1.88 to 2.23 which indicated that these items did not meet the criterion mean of 2.50. However, the grand mean of 2.46 apparently showed that modern technologies are rarely utilized for teaching business education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The standard deviation of the fifteen items in the scale ranged from 0.70 to 0.97 which showed that the responses of the respondents were not too far from the mean and to one another

Research Question 4: *What are the challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.4: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
1.	Integrating modern technologies into teaching business education courses is often challenging due to limited access to resources and technical support.	3.12	0.77	Agree
2.	Difficulty arises in adapting teaching methods to incorporate modern technological tools effectively for business education instruction.	3.29	0.73	Agree
3.	Barriers such as inadequate training hinder the seamless integration of modern technologies into the curriculum for teaching business education.	3.10	0.76	Agree
4.	Accessing and utilizing modern technological resources pose consistent challenges in delivering high-quality instruction for business education.	2.99	0.93	Agree
5.	Selecting appropriate technological tools for teaching business education courses presents significant challenges for effective instruction.	2.83	0.60	Agree
6.	Integrating technology into existing curricula can be challenging, requiring significant updates to course content and structure.	3.46	0.63	Agree
7.	Inadequate technical support can impede the effective utilization of modern technologies for teaching business education courses.	3.24	0.73	Agree
8.	Accessibility and inclusivity of modern technologies into business education instruction is faced with various barriers.	3.05	0.77	Agree
9.	Resistance from colleagues or institutional policies can complicate efforts to incorporate modern technologies into teaching business education.	2.86	0.97	Agree
10.	Keeping pace with rapid technological advancements poses challenges in effectively utilizing modern technologies for teaching business education.	2.89	0.82	Agree
11.	Lack of resources hampers efforts to keep up with the evolving technological landscape in business education.	3.23	0.70	Agree
12.	Inadequate infrastructure hinder the seamless integration of modern technologies into the curriculum.	3.11	0.78	Agree
13.	Limited access to technology is a major challenge as all students may not have equal access to devices, internet, or specific software, creating a digital divide.	3.60	0.66	Strongly Agree
14.	The institution might lack the basic infrastructure, such as reliable internet or up-to-date hardware, to support modern technology.	3.62	0.65	Strongly Agree
15.	Digital distractions is a challenge faced by students as they might be easily distracted by social media notifications, or other online content, reducing their focus on learning.	3.16	0.84	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.17	0.76	Agree

Table 4.4 revealed that the mean responses of the respondents on all fifteen items ranged from 2.83 to 3.62 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. However, the grand mean of 3.17 apparently showed that Business Education Lecturers are faced with so much challenges in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

The standard deviation of the fifteen items in the scale ranged from 0.63 to 0.97 which disclosed that the responses of the respondents were not far apart from the mean and to one another.

Research Question 5: *What are the remedies to challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.5: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on remedies to challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
1.	Invest in infrastructure by upgrading school infrastructure to support modern technology, including reliable internet and updated hardware.	3.26	0.85	Agree
2.	Provide devices or laptops for lecturers and students to ensure equal access to technology.	3.52	0.63	Strongly Agree
3.	Utilize cloud-based solutions to reduce infrastructure costs and increase accessibility.	3.16	0.83	Agree
4.	Provide regular training and professional development opportunities for lecturers to enhance their technical skills.	3.59	0.62	Strongly Agree
5.	Establish mentorship programmes where experienced lecturers can guide and support their peers.	3.45	0.76	Agree
6.	Ensure that there is adequate technical support for lecturers to troubleshoot issues and provide assistance.	3.14	0.85	Agree
7.	Establish clear guidelines for technology use in the classroom to minimize distractions.	3.45	0.76	Agree
8.	Design interactive learning experiences that engage students and promote active learning.	3.45	0.76	Agree
9.	Teach students digital literacy skills to help them effectively use technology for learning.	3.79	0.45	Strongly Agree
10.	Regularly review and update the curriculum to ensure it aligns with modern technologies and industry needs.	3.64	0.55	Strongly Agree
11.	Utilize open educational resources to provide students with access to relevant and up-to-date content.	3.37	0.79	Agree
12.	Provide cyber-security training for lecturers and students to raise awareness about online safety and security.	3.46	0.76	Agree
13.	Allocate a specific budget for technology integration and maintenance.	3.40	0.67	Agree
14.	Explore grants and funding opportunities to support technology integration.	3.09	0.87	Agree
15.	Establish partnerships with technology companies or organizations to access resources and support.	3.34	0.80	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.41	0.73	Agree

The mean responses of the respondents on all the items in Table 4.5 ranged from 3.09 to 3.79, which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. However, the grand mean of 3.41 demonstrated that the respondents agreed that all the items in the scale are remedies to the challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in the utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The standard deviation of the fifteen items in the scale ranged from

0.45 to 0.87, which indicated that the responses of the respondents were close to the mean and to one another

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on the extent to which modern technologies are available for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Table 4.6: T-test analysis of male and female respondents’ mean ratings on extent to which modern technologies are available in teaching Business Education

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	71	2.76	0.98					
Female	69	2.42	0.55	138	0.05	2.52	0.01	S

Data presented in Table 4.6 connoted that the t-value on extent to which modern technologies are available for teaching Business Education courses is 2.52 while the p-value is 0.01. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents’ mean ratings on extent to which modern technologies are available for teaching Business Education courses. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between universities and colleges of education lecturers on the extent to which modern technologies are adequate for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4.7: T-test analysis of male and female respondents’ mean ratings on the extent to which modern technologies are adequate for teaching Business Education courses

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Universities	43	2.77	0.87					
College of Education	97	2.76	0.92	138	0.05	0.03	0.98	NS

Data presented in Table 4.7 connoted that the t-value on extent to which modern technologies are adequate for teaching Business Education courses is 0.03 while the p-value is 0.98. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of universities and colleges of education respondents’ mean ratings on extent to which modern technologies are adequate for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of respondents on the extent to which modern technologies are utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on qualification.

Table 4.8: Shows the descriptive statistics of ANOVA summary on extent to which modern technologies are utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on Educational qualification.

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
B.Ed /B.Sc(Ed)	10	2.30	.483
M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed)	82	2.13	.750
PhD	48	2.15	.825
Total	140	2.15	.758

Table 4.9: ANOVA summary on extent to which modern technologies are utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on Educational qualification.

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Level of Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.246	2	.123	.212	0.81	NS
Within Groups	79.604	137	.581			
Total	79.850	139				

Note: Level of Significant = 0.05, NS = Not Significant

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) in Table 4.9 indicated that the p-value of 0.81 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implied that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of the business education lecturers with B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed), M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed), and PhD qualification on extent to which modern technologies are utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on Educational qualification. This signified that educational qualification of the respondents is not a significant source of difference in their responses. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean responses of business education lecturers on extent to which modern technologies are utilized for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on Educational qualification was accepted.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers on challenges encountered in the utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4.10: T-test analysis of male and female respondents' mean ratings on challenges encountered in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	71	3.11	0.77					
Female	69	3.13	0.78	138	0.05	-0.14	0.89	NS

Data presented in Table 4.10 insinuated that the t-value on challenges encountered in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses is -0.14 while the p-value is 0.89. This purported that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents' mean ratings on challenges encountered in the utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of respondents on remedies to the challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on educational qualification.

Table 4.11: Shows the descriptive statistics of ANOVA on remedies to the challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses based on Educational qualification.

Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
B.Ed /B.Sc(Ed)	10	3.00	.943
M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed)	82	3.29	.728
PhD	48	3.27	1.005
Total	140	3.26	.845

Table 4.11: Shows the descriptive statistics of ANOVA on remedies to challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses based on educational qualification

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.767	2	.383	.533	0.59	NS
Within Groups	98.455	137	.719			
Total	99.221	139				

Note: Level of Significant = 0.05, NS = Not Significant

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) in Table 4.12 connoted that the p-value of 0.59 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This signified that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of the business education lecturers with B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed), M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed), and PhD qualification on remedies to challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses based on educational qualification. This showed that educational qualification of the respondents is not a significant source of difference in their responses. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean responses of business education lecturers on remedies to challenges encountered by Business Education lecturers in utilization of modern technologies for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on educational qualification was accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results addressing research question one indicated that modern instructional technologies are moderately available for the delivery of Business Education courses across tertiary institutions in Delta State. Technologies identified as moderately available include Learning Management Systems, Google Classroom, smartphones, laptops, Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, Virtual Reality (VR), Canvas, Zoom, Google Meet, and Google Docs. This observation aligns with the report by Wokocho et al. (2017), who noted the presence of e-learning tools in business education instruction. Similarly, Anetu et al. (2020) acknowledged the availability of selected digital learning platforms. Larry (2016) also affirmed that computers were accessible in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

However, the present findings contrast with those of Egomo et al. (2012), who emphasized a severe deficiency in ICT infrastructure across Nigerian universities, with exceptions made for basic tools like laptops, projectors, and internet services. Likewise, Akpojotor (2022) reported that computer labs lacked the capacity to effectively deliver practical lessons. This study also diverges from Odike et al. (2023), who found a lack of ICT resources in government-owned colleges of education in Enugu State. Further disagreement is noted with Ado and Amoor (2021), who concluded that contemporary blended learning tools were largely unavailable in business education programs. Lastly, the findings do not support Ademiluyi (2019), who stated that ICT resources were scarcely available in institutions.

Concerning research question two, the findings suggest that modern technologies are moderately adequate for teaching Business Education courses in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Tools such as Learning Management Systems, Google Classroom, smartphones, laptops, AI applications, VR platforms, Canvas, and Zoom were found to be moderately sufficient for instructional purposes. This contradicts the assertion of Oluwadare et al. (2019), who observed that modern infrastructure necessary for effective business education was not adequately available. Similarly, Umoeshiet (2015) highlighted the inadequacy of instructional resources, which discouraged educators from integrating technology into their teaching practices. Additionally, Akpojotor (2021) reported insufficient availability of modern teaching technologies.

Regarding research question three, the results revealed that most modern technologies are rarely utilized in teaching Business Education courses in Delta State's tertiary institutions. Specific tools such as

Learning Management Systems, Google Classroom, tablets, projectors, interactive whiteboards, Canvas, Zoom, Google Meet, and Google Docs are underutilized in instructional delivery. This finding supports Anetu et al. (2020), who noted limited use of some e-learning platforms. It is also consistent with the study by Inije et al. (2013), which indicated low usage of e-learning resources in colleges of education. Furthermore, it agrees with Crossdale and Nwosu (2022), who reported that digital tools such as electronic boards, digital libraries, and scanners were minimally used, and that e-learning implementation in business education was only moderately adopted.

The findings are further corroborated by Iyamu and Onaivi (2021), who emphasized the unavailability and underutilization of digital learning resources among students and lecturers. Similarly, Ado and Amoor (2021) reported that blended learning technologies were not in practical use. Finally, this study's results differ from those of Ademiluyi (2019), who found that ICT tools were generally unused in the instruction of business-related subjects in public secondary schools in Osun State.

Research question four explored the challenges faced by Business Education lecturers in using modern technologies for instructional purposes in tertiary institutions across Delta State. The study revealed that lecturers encounter multiple difficulties, including restricted access to digital tools and technical assistance, lack of training, difficulty in integrating technology into traditional teaching practices, poor infrastructure, institutional resistance, and digital distractions among students. These findings are consistent with Akpojotor (2022), who reported that the cost of implementing digitalization in business education in Delta State was high. The study also supports the observations of Wokocha et al. (2017), who emphasized that various hindrances affect the availability of e-learning facilities for undergraduate instruction.

Additionally, the results echo those of Iyamu and Onaivi (2021) and Akpojotor (2022), who noted several barriers to effective digital integration, including poor funding, unavailability of trained personnel, unstable electricity supply, and inadequate computer hardware. In agreement with Igberaharha (2014), this study also found a shortage of qualified and experienced lecturers proficient in modern educational technologies.

For research question five, the findings demonstrated that all proposed items in the scale were considered valid solutions to the challenges identified. These recommendations include: increasing investment in technological infrastructure, supplying laptops and devices to both lecturers and students, adopting cloud-based tools for greater accessibility, offering continuous professional development and training, establishing mentorship schemes, ensuring technical support, implementing clear usage policies, and designing engaging digital learning experiences. Other strategies identified were: teaching digital literacy skills, updating the curriculum regularly, promoting the use of open educational resources, providing cybersecurity education, setting dedicated budgets for tech integration, seeking external funding or grants, and partnering with tech-oriented organizations. These remedies were considered effective by respondents and align with Akpojotor (2022), who advocated for management support through ongoing staff development programmes.

Hypotheses Testing

- Hypothesis One tested gender differences in the perceived availability of modern technologies for Business Education. The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between male and female lecturers, indicating that gender influenced their responses. This is contrary to Nwokike and Uwaneze (2016), who reported no significant gender-based difference among accounting teachers regarding the use of new technologies in Rivers State secondary schools.
- Hypothesis Two examined the difference in perceptions between university and college of education lecturers on the adequacy of modern technology. The result showed no significant difference, suggesting a shared perception across both institution types.
- Hypothesis Three assessed the influence of educational qualification on the extent of technology usage. The findings indicated no significant difference among lecturers with B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed), M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed), and Ph.D. qualifications, implying that qualification level did not impact usage frequency.

- Hypothesis Four investigated gender differences in challenges faced during technology utilization. The outcome showed no significant difference in responses, suggesting that male and female lecturers experience similar difficulties.
- Hypothesis Five focused on whether educational qualification influenced views on solutions to identified challenges. The findings revealed no significant difference, indicating that lecturers at all qualification levels agree on the proposed remedies for improving technology use in Business Education instruction.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the integration of modern technologies in the teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institutions across Delta State is minimal. Business Education lecturers encounter numerous obstacles in effectively using these technologies, which negatively impact teaching delivery. Furthermore, a statistically significant difference was observed between the perceptions of male and female lecturers regarding the availability of modern instructional technologies in Business Education classrooms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Provision of Facilities: Tertiary institution authorities should ensure the adequate supply of technological tools such as computer tablets, internet access, scanners, projectors, and interactive whiteboards for Business Education programmes.
2. Monitoring Usage: Management should regularly supervise Business Education lecturers to encourage consistent and effective utilization of the available technological resources in their instructional practices.
3. Investment by Stakeholders: Stakeholders, including government agencies and private sponsors, should invest in upgrading technological infrastructure to keep pace with the dynamic trends in Business Education.
4. Capacity Building: Continuous professional development and training workshops should be organized to enhance lecturers' competence in using modern instructional technologies.
5. Enforcement of Policy: Institutional policymakers should introduce and enforce policies mandating the use of modern technologies, with penalties for non-compliance by lecturers.
6. Replication of Study: Similar research should be replicated in other regions to validate the findings and expand understanding of the issue from a broader geographical perspective.

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